

Curriculum Vitae

Name: Hind Bushra Ahmed Ibrahim

Place of Birth: Omdurman/Sudan

Contact address: Ahfad University for Women- School of Rural Extension, Education and Development

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Civil Status: Married/ with two children

Language/s: Arabic mother tongue / English instrumental language

Graduate from/ year: School of Rural Extension Education and Development (REED), Ahfad University for Women (AUW) 1994.

Degree Awarded / year: Bachelor of Art in Rural Development, School of Rural Extension Education and Development (REED), Ahfad University for Women (AUW) 1994.

Current position/year Associate Professor of Sustainable Rural Development in School of Rural Extension, Education and Development (REED), Ahfad University for Women, since 2014 to date.

Other academic qualifications:

- Doctor of philosophy (Ph.D.) Sustainable Rural Development, in area of livelihood and Cooperate Social Responsibility (CSR). **2014**
- Master of Science Degree (M.A) in Population and Development, faculty of Economics and Rural Development, Applied Statistical and Demography Department, Gezira University, Sudan . **1998**.

1- Training of Trainers:

- Training workshop on Basic of Social Research Methods to postgraduate Students of Sudanese Universities. Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with Skim project Sudan 2022, project activities. Nov. 2022.
- Training on Community capacity development Community conversation training, Kadogli locality, South Kordofan State, Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with Norwegian Church AID. 22-30 Oct.. 2022.
- Gender Mainstreaming in Project Cycle North Kordofan State, Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with IFAD. 12-18 March 2022.

- Training on leadership (facilitation), Economic Empowerment of Female Urban Agricultural labors, Project: ElSourab Area, Karary Locality Khartoum State. Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with Italian Agency for Development Cooperation in Sudan. Oct. 2020-April 2021.
- Training on Small project planning and management, Economic Empowerment of Female Urban Agricultural labors, Project: ElSourab Area, Karary Locality Khartoum State. Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with Italian Agency for Development Cooperation in Sudan. Oct. 2020-April 2021.
- Community mobilization skills for midwives (facilitation), Obstetrical & Gynecology society of Sudan (OGss) Ahfad University for women North Kordofan state.1-3Feb.2018.
- Communication skills, leadership and time management for midwives(facilitation) Obstetrical & Gynecology society of Sudan (OGss) Ahfad University for women North Kordofan state.20-22Jan.2018.
- Effective communication skills, and Effective Team work workshop for community member (facilitation),Kulana ElTanmia project, Al-HajYosif area British Council in collaboration with Ahfad University for Women. **6-7 Oct.2017.**
- Formation and community organization workshop,(facilitation) KulanaElTanima project, Al-HajYosif area British Council in collaboration with Ahfad University for Women. 20-21 May.2017.
- Empowering rural women farmers workshop (coordination and facilitation) FAO in collaboration with Ahfad University for Women. July 2016- March 2017.
- TOT training Workshop onthe Saleema Communication Initiative, (facilitation) in three states, North Kordfoan, East Darfour and Norht Darfour.April-may2016.
- Findings of a seasonal livelihoods programming consultation(facilitation) World Food Program(WFP)in collaboration with Ahfad University for WomenPort Sudan State, Sudan 31 Jan- 4 Feb. 2016.
- TOT workshop of Parent and Teachers association (PTA) training, (facilitation), GIZ organization collaborating with Ahfad University for Women. 1-30 Sept. 2014.
- Findings of a seasonal livelihoods programming consultation(facilitation) World Food Program(WFP)in collaboration with Ahfad University for Women.Kassala State, Sudan 24-28 August, 2014.

- Findings of a seasonal livelihoods programming consultation (facilitation) World Food Program (WFP) in collaboration with Ahfad University for Women, North Darfur – Sudan EL Fasher, 22-26 June 2014.
- Intergeneration dialogue workshop, (facilitation) Gender and reproductive Health & rights Resource Center (GRACE) in collaboration with UNFPA. June 2014
- Skills based training in community intervention for combating FGM, (facilitation) Gender and reproductive Health & rights Resource Center (GRACE) in collaboration with UNHCR Eritrea. 5-9th May 2014.
- Communication skills, community mobilization and concentrated language encounter (CLE) for women workshop. (Facilitation) Babiker Bedri scientific Association for Women studies collaboration with Switzerland embassy May 2013 and Nov. 2013.
- Participatory approaches for needs assessment and Training on Small enterprise for War victims (facilitation) 2012 in Damazeen .
- A course designed to train Internally Displaced Women (IDPs) on Community Forestry (facilitation) at Ahfad University for Women, farm project 6 June-30 June.
- Small project workshop for IDPs women (facilitation) collaboration with Switzerland Embassy and Ahfad University for Women. May 2006.
- Youth Peer Education training on Reproductive Health focusing on HIV/ AIDs (coordination, facilitation) in Southern Sudan (Juba), Planned Parenthood Federation of American International collaborating with UNCIF, Network for Youth and Adolescent of Africa (NAYA). Jun 2005
- Youth Peer Education training on Reproductive Health focusing on HIV/ AIDs in Khartoum, (coordination and facilitation) Planned Parenthood Federation of American International collaborating with UNICEF, Network for Youth and Adolescent of American. **May 2005**
- Youth Peer Education training on Reproductive Health focusing on HIV/ AIDs in Eastern Sudan (Elshowk area) (coordination and facilitation) Planned Parenthood Federation of American International collaborating with UNICEF, African Youth network (NYA) . **Feb. 2005**
- Evaluation mission for the IRC's development projects (coordinator) in Kassla area. IRC in collaboration with AUW. May 2003.
- Community Based Organization training (coordinator and facilitation) in five villages in Northern Omdurman area. Babiker Bedri scientific Association for Women studies AUW. March 2001.

- The voluntary work and rules of establishing new Community Based Organization (CBOs) workshop (coordination and facilitation) in five villages in Gezira area. Babiker Bedri scientific Association for Women studies AUW. May 2000.

2. Consultancies:

- Member in the study on Understanding Barriers and Enablers to Women's Leadership in Sudan” Project hosted at the Middle East Centre, London School of Economics and Political Science” Sept-Nov.2022.
- Co-consultant of research on The Impact of the COVID-19 on family cohesion and the economic, social and health conditions in Sudan: a quantitative and qualitative research among the Sudanese family in five states. Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with Doha International Family Institute (DIFI) Qatar. . 2021-2022
- A Baseline Survey for Nourishing People and the Earth through Inclusive and Sustainable Agriculture for Integrated Agriculture and Marketing Development Project (IAMDP). Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with IFAD/NORAD FINANCED GRANT .May- June. 2022.
- Co-consultant of A baseline study to address the economic impact of COVID-19 in Refugee camps in White Nile State (three camps). Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with ADRA. Nov.2021- Feb. 2022.
- Coordinator of the Drying vegetables activity, The Economic Empowerment of Female Urban Agricultural labors, Project: ElSourab Area ,Karary Locality Khartoum State. Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with Italian Agency for Development Cooperation in Sudan. Nov.2020-April 2021.
- Co-consultant of baseline study of the Countering the economic impact of covid-19 in refugee camps in White Nile State (CEIRC). Ahfad University for Women &AADRA organization. Nov.2020-March 2021.
- ***Team member*** (represented ofAUW University) in Technical team on the Strengthen of Demographic Window research program for all States in Sudan, under supervision of National Population Council. Sudan. (**May 2018 up to date**)

The responsibilities of Technical Team are:

- ✓ Collect all documents experiences from different countries related to demographic window (investment of youth).
- ✓ Prepare road map for demographic window.
- ✓ Prepare different Seminar sessions for different ministries to elaborate the concept of demographic window.
- ✓ Prepare analytical report about demographic situation in Sudan with emphasis on demographic changes and determined demographic opportunities and challenges.
- ✓ Prepare meeting with professional consultants for revision and improvement of road map.
- ✓ Give and work with the improvement road map.
- ✓ Prepare final report.
- ***Team leader of the survey & Field work*** for the study on The Improvement of Omdurman Locality Neighborhoods Community Centers project. Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with the European Union.(**2018-March 2019**)
- ***Field coordinator*** on Role of Female Farmers in Urban Agriculture in Khartoum State: Challenges and Opportunities. School of Rural Extension, Education & Development (REED) – Ahfad University for Women & the Italian Agency for Development.(**5-15 May 2018**)
- ***Consultant of Advocacy and Events*** British Council project: promoting Civic Engagement of Secondary School Girls in AlHaj Yousif Area. This is a project that aims at enhancing the university outreach in the area of education at the same time it is working to facilitate secondary school female students voicing their problems. (**2015-2018**)
- ***Field & research coordinator of*** Child protection program: measuring and monitoring change in social norms around the practices of FGM (team leader).Ahfad University for Women Collaboration with UNCIEF and NCCW. White Nile State. **25Nov.-3Dec.2017.**
- ***Project coordinator*** of Technical Support to Rural Women Farmers project, Food and Agricultural organization of the United Nations in Sudan (FAO) in collaboration with Ahfad University for Women (School of REED).(June **2016-Jan.2017**).It focusses on:

- Capacity Building of women farmers in different issues such, Leadership skills and Working in groups, Introduction of vegetable culture practices and marketing information management, Food security and home garden vegetables production and their nutritional values and,.....etc.
- Rehabilitation of the Nursery Training Centre.

➤ ***Filed work coordinator*** of House- to- House Education to Engage Rural Women and Youth as active Agents for Prevention of FGM/C and Early Forced marriage project in three states Khartoum State, Kassala State and Gadarif State. Ahfad University for women in collaboration with the Canadian Embassy Khartoum. **(2014-2016)**. It focuses on:

- Three-days training sessions for 150 women and 75 youth in communication and mobilization skills on FGM/C and early forced marriage

- Identification of 10 women and 5 youth for the establishment of a Village Child Protection Group in each of the 15 villages through consultation with community leaders.

- Day meetings for development of the Village Child Protection Group Action Plans for promotion of women and girl's health and prevention of FGM/C and early forced marriage.

➤ ***Research Coordinator of*** Baseline study for Joint Resilience- Building project (JRP) in 4 localities in kassla State. WFP in collaboration with AUW. **(June-August 2015)**

➤ ***Co- Consultant/ Health and Gender Specialist*** of final assessment of Food Security Livelihoods program in Jabait Maadin Locality Red Sea, Sudanese Red Crescent /Spanish Red Cross and European Union. **14-20 June 2015**

➤ ***Research Coordinator*** May- in Developing Indicators and developed tools for baseline survey for combating FGM, Gender and reproductive Health &rights Resource Center (GRACE)at AUW in collaboration with UNFPA. **Sep.2014-2015.**

➤ ***Research/ Field work coordinator,***of Mid –assessment of Dutch Consort for Rehabilitation (DCR) program in Darfour State (four Localities). **21Jan- 8Feb 2014**

➤ ***Team Leader and field supervisor,*** Of base line assessment survey on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) of Kenena Sugar Company on community livelihood – Mamoun Bahariy social research center. **Augt 2010-May 2011**

- **Team leader** of base line survey on the revolving fund project for poor women headed household in Roro village in Damazeen area. Arab Authority for Agriculture Investment and Development (AAAID).. **3-8 Jan. 2007**
- **Research coordinator** of Social Economic Impact Research on Agadi project in El Damazeen area. Collaborated with Arab Authority for Agriculture Investment and Development (AAAID) and Northmbira University in U.K.Feb **2006**
- **Senior facilitator& field work supervisor** on Community Development Fund (CDF) Facilitation and Intermediation project in Kassla and hamshkoribe localities – Kassla State (40 villages) World Bank collaboration Ahfad University for Women,. **1-30 Nov.2006**. The main activities are:
 - Baseline survey for Need assessment
 - Preparing people for the selection of CBOs
 - Train the member of the CBOs
 - Train people about how to development of community action plan (CAP).
- **Research coordinator** of base line survey on the Revolving Fund project for poor women in Hamarat Elskhik village - Northern Kordofan. Arab Authority for Agriculture Investment and Development (AAAID). **7-14 Aug. 2006**.

iii) At International level

- **Research coordinator** and team leader of base line survey on the Revolving Fund project for poor women headed household in Sograta Island in Republic of Yemen. Aug. **2008.AAAID**
- **Research coordinator** and Team leader of base line survey on the revolving fund project for poor women headed household in Republic of Mauritania. **June 2008**
- Coordinator for supervising and monitoring tow Revolving fund programs in Republic of Mauritania, Yemen and Comoros. **AAAID. AAAID. 2008-2009**

3. Publications and research:

A. Referred papers/ articles

A1. Accepted papers:

- Badri Amria , Ahmed Hind, 2022, Measuring the COVID-19 knowledge, Attitudes and Practice (KAP) : A survey among society in Khartoum State. International Union of Universities Journal.
- Ahmed Hind,2020, The Influence of conflict on the Women livelihood – Attach camp- Darfur State-Sudan. International journal of Economics, Commerce and Management. United Kingdom.

- Ahmed Hind & Janet Habeel, Zubida Hamid and Niveen Osma, 2019, Fish farms experience: Opportunities and Challenges, Khartoum State (Al-Kharṭūm Bahri locality) – Sudan International journal of Economics, Commerce and Management. United Kingdom. *(in publishing process(required fees)+ Attached acceptance letter)*
- Ahmed Hind, 2017 The Role of Arab Sudanese Blue Nile Agricultural Company (ASBNACO) Corporate Social Responsibility on Community Livelihood- case Study Agadi Village, Blue Nile State. Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal. *(in publishing process(required fees)+ Attached acceptance letter)*.

A2. Submitted papers / policy brief

- Policy brief on Community resilience, socio-economic partnerships and sociocultural behavioural change: Practical ways to manage the COVID19 pandemic crisis, in Task Force Title: Covid-19: Multidisciplinary Approaches to Complex Problems of T20 Saudi Arabia. Ahfad Journal
- Ahmed Hind, , Marwi dam construction: opportunities and challenges on community livelihoods in Alhamdab village (2&3). International journal of Economics, Commerce and Management. United Kingdom. Vol. VI. Issue, November 2018. ISSN23480386
- The Role of School Feeding Program Supported by DAL Company in Students' Enrolment and Drop-out. Ahmed Alradi Gaber Alamel Schools in Omdurman - Ombada Locality. Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal – Vol.4, No.2. Jan. 2017.
- Ahmed Hind, 2015, Women Empowerment Through IFADs Development Project, Aug. 2015 “Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal – Vol.4, No.15.
- Ahmed Hind, 2015, The Effect of Kenena Sugar Company on Community Livelihood: A case of Altogaba Village, White Nile State, Sudan, International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies Volume, Issue3, March 2015, PP19-29 ISSN2394-6288(print)&ISSN2394-6296(online).

B) Books:

- Ahmed Bushra Hind, The influence of Kenena Sugar Company on Community Livelihood (2015), printed by books on Demand GmbH, scholars' press, Germany.

C) Monographs / Manuals:

- Training manual in Integration of gender in all stages of development projects 2022. Regional Institute for Gender, Diversity, Peace and Rights Studies in cooperation with the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD).

- Training manual on Community Organization, Formation, and Mobilization, Communication and Networking, Ahfad University for Women collaboration with British Council. **Feb. 2017.**

- Training manual on communication skills, community mobilization for concentrated language encounter (CLE). Babiker Bedri scientific Association for Women studies collaboration with Switzerland embassy **2013.**

- Manual on mobilizing, organizing and empowering communities for collective planning, School of REED, Ahfad University for Women .2007.

- Small stories for Adult Education learners in form of manual, Ahfad University for women, 2006.

D) Reports& studies

- Baseline Survey on Agricultural Value Chain Development Project (AVCDP), Community Mobilization Program West Kordofan State. African Development Bank - Ministry of Agriculture and Forests. 2021.

- Evaluation study on The Influence of Omdurman Locality Neighborhoods Community Centers project on community and youth. Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with the European Union. Nov 2018- March.2019.

- Analytical Report on the social and economic conditions of rural, nomadic and coastal women in Arab countries. Ahfad University for Women in collaboration with the league of Arab States, Arab Organization for Agricultural Development. **Dec.2016.**

- Findings of a seasonal livelihoods programming consultation,Port Sudan State , Sudan 31 Jan- 4 Feb. 2016.

- Final Evaluation for the Food Security/ Livelihoods program in Jabait Maadin Locality Red Sea,14-**20June 2015.**Conducted for the Sudanese Red Crescent /Spanish Red Cross and European Union.

- Baseline study for the Joint Resilience-Building Project(JRP) in 4 Localities in Kassala State Ahfad University for Women collaboration with **WFP Sept.2015.**

- House- to House Education toEngage rural Women and Youth as active Agents for Prevention of FGM/Cand Early Forced Marriage.Ahfad University for Women collaboration with Canadian Embassy **Nov2014-Feb.2015**

- Baseline study to develop indicators for FGM abandonment in four States, Ahfad University for Women collaboration with UNFPA, **Dec. 2014.**
- Findings of a seasonal livelihoods programming consultation, Kassala State, Sudan 24-28 August, 2014
- Findings of a seasonal livelihoods programming consultation, North Darfur – Sudan EL Fasher, 22-26 JUNE 2014.
- Mid –assessment study of Dutch Consort for Rehabilitation (DCR) program in Darfour State (four Localities). **June 2014.**
 - Study on Corporate Social Responsibility of Kenena Sugar Company on community livelihood (10 villages), Mamoun Behariy Center for Social and Economic Studies 2012.
 - Social Economic Impact Research on Agadi project in El Damazeen area. Collaborated with Arab Authority for Agriculture Investment and Development (AAID) and Northmbira University in U.K. **2007.**

E) Papers presented at international conferences

(i) Abstracts published in conferences proceedings

- Elderly Experience in Nursing Homes: Situational Analysis Khartoum State, presented in the International Symposium on Elderly. Under theme: Never Too Late for Elderly Well- being, International Federation for Home Economic. AUW. Feb.2018.
- The Role of School Feeding program supported by DAL Company in Students' Enrolment and Drop-out Ahmed Alradi Gaber and Alamel School in Omdurman - Ombada Locality. Presented in The first International Conference on Child nutrition & Man-Made Crisis. AUW- Sudan **Dec.2016**
- Baseline study to develop indicators for FGM abandonment, presented in International Knowledge Sharing Conference on Women and Girls' Health in Sudan, 19th-22nd October 2015. Khartoum-Sudan. **Oct. 2015.**

(ii) Abstracts presented at scientific conferences:

- Exploring the Impacts of Internal Displaced People (IDPs) camp on Livelihood of host communities presented in Conference on Social Sciences October 17-21-2022 NORDSC.
- The Status of Women working in Factory - A fro Tac Factory- Omdurman – Sudan: will be presented in 18th International Conference on Corporate Social Responsibility

(CSR). Under the theme “*Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): public and private sector perspectives*”, Portugal. **Sep.2019 (upcoming)** (Accepted paper to present in conference).

- The Role of Arab Sudanese Blue Nile Agricultural Company (ASBNACO) Corporate Social Responsibility on community Livelihood Case study: Agadi village, Blue Nile State, Sudan, presented in Takaful Annual Conference. The John DGerhart Center for Philanthropy, Civic Engagement and responsible Business at American University in Cairo- Egypt.Oct.2017
- Knowledge, Attitude and practice of Men towards Contraception-Umbdda area. Presented in 29 th annual seminar on population and Development, Cairo Demographic Center (CDC) Cairo- Egypt. Dec. 1999.

F) Accepted chapter

Hind Bushra, Livelihood Development through Kenena Sugar Company’s CSR Case study of Fongoga Cluster Community, in *New Innovations in Economics, Business and Management* Vol. 4. eBook ISBN: 978-93-5547-408-7

G) Reviewer in International Journal

- International Business Research; Vol. 14, No. 12; 2021 ISSN 1913-9004 E-ISSN 1913-9012 Published by Canadian Center of Science and Education.
- International Journal of Environment and Climate Change, India: Guest House Road, Street no - 1/6, Hooghly, West Bengal, India,, Tele: +91 8617752708, UK: Third Floor, 207 Regent Street, London, W1B 3HH, UK, Fax: +44 20-3031-1429 .
- International Journal of Plant & Soil Science, India: Guest House Road, Street no - 1/6, Hooghly, West Bengal, India,, Tele: +91 8617752708, UK: Third Floor, 207 Regent Street, London, W1B 3HH, UK, Fax: +44 20-3031-1429.
- Reviewer in Journal of Economics and Technology Research, : <http://www.scholink.org/ojs/index.php/jetr>. Los Angeles.
- Reviewer International Journal of Business Administration ISSN: 1923-4007; E-ISSN: 1923-4015.

(iii) Participation in International Live Webinars:

- Webinar on Policies Needed to Support Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals, taking into consideration the many current challenges in the Arab Region.

EMR-SDG Learning Platform In Collaboration with League of Arab States
Directorate for Sustainable Development and International Cooperation Organizes.
Thursday 15 October 2020, 12:00 – 13:30 Cairo time (10:00 – 11:30 UTC)

- Ahmed.Hind. 2020, live webinar on “Crisis for Sustainability?” Department of Banking Finance, National PG Lucknow. 28.7.2020 time from 1:30pm- 3:00pm.
Ahmed .Hind. 2020, Information Note on the Covid-19 in Sudan, presented in EMR-SDG Learning Platform Webinar on COVID-19 Inequities in the Arab Countries 21 July 2020, 12:00 – 13:30 Cairo time (10:00 – 11:30 UTC). American University in Cairo.

Addresses of three reputable referees:

- **Dr. Gasim Badri, president of Ahfad University for Women**
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- **Prof Shadia Abdelrahim Mohammed**
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- **Prof Balghis Badri , head of the Regional Institute for Gender, Diversity, Peace and Rights,**
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